

Morphological Characters, Effects of System of Rice Intensification (SRI) and Green Manure on Growth and Yield of Selected Rice Varieties from Kawa Township

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Abstract

This study was carried out to study the morphological characters and to determine the appropriate seedlings age for Five Selected Rice Varieties in the System of Rice Intensification by using green manure. Field experiments were conducted at the field of Thabyu Village, Kawa Township, during wet season 2016. The green manure plants, *Samanea saman* (Kokko) were used as basal fertilizer. Among the five varieties, Sinthukha variety gave the highest grain yields and tiller numbers. By comparing seedling ages, 8 and 10 days old seedling were significantly higher than those of 12 and 14 days old seedling. Systems of rice intensification (SRI) methods were able to improve rice growth and performance at both the vegetative and reproductive stages.

Introduction

Rice is one of the most important crops grown in Myanmar and is the staple food for the whole nation. Future rice production depends on how people improve the water use efficiency of the rice crop. Reducing amount of water in irrigated rice production has become a matter of global concern and water saving irrigation techniques have received renewed attention. The system of rice intensification (SRI) was developed in Madagascar in the early 1980's. (SRI) has been promoted for more than a decade as a set of agronomic management practices for rice cultivation and enhances the yield and reduces water requirements (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). Organic manures especially green manures, (GMS) are a potentially feasible means of improving soil fertility and physical properties (Mann and Garrity, 1994). Legumes have a symbiotic relationship with bacteria called *rhizobium*. *Rhizobium* normally lives in the soil but, when there is limited soil nitrogen; legumes release flavonoids which signal to *rhizobium* that the plant is seeking symbiotic bacteria. The bacteria convert the nitrogen into compounds which can be utilized by the plants. When leguminous plants die and decompose; their nitrogen compounds enrich the soil and become important components of crop relation systems (Portelli, 2013). *Samanea saman* (Kokko) is belong to family Mimosaceae and were selected as green manure plants which were very abundant wild growing in study area.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site and materials

The tested varieties were grown during July to October 2016 as monsoon rice at the Farm of Thabyu Village, Kawa Township by using System of Rise Intensification (SRI) method. The Five Commercial Rice Varieties used in the experiment were -

V₁ = Sinthukha

V₂ = Shwewarhtun

V₃ = Yarkyaw

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V₄ = Manawthukha

V₅ = Byauehtun

Collection and Preparation of green manure plants

The well ripens seeds of *Samanea saman* (Kokko) were collected around the Thabyu Village, one of the study areas. After treating the pre-germination test, 20 seeds for each pot were soaked in water for 24 hours and incubated 12 hours. After that, the seeds were broadcasted into ploughed experimental pots. Sprinkling water was using to succeed the germination.

Preparation the experimental plot

Arrangement the two hundred pots were assigned with five replications at four treatments for five rice varieties. The pot size was 22 cm in wide and 30 cm in depth. 4.5 kg of soil were evenly added in each pot. Before sowing legumes, the soil from plot had been tested in Land Use Department of Myanmar Agriculture Service (MAS).

Preparation process of green manure fertilizer

After 45 days, green manure crops were ploughed and buried in the pots for monsoon rice cultivation. Application of 10 days interval, the green manure plants have already decomposed into organic matter. The soil content of biomass yield is also tested. The fresh *Samanea saman* were tested for nitrogen content in Myanmar Food Process and Exporters Associated (MFPEA) Food Industries Development Supporting Laboratory FIDSL.

Seedbed preparation for Raising Seedlings

To transplant four different seedlings age of five varieties at the same date, twenty seedbeds for each seedling age were separately prepared in July 2016. The size of one seedbed was 1 × 1 sq. ft and raise above the original soil level. Seedbed was covered with plastic sheet and then lay down the mixture of cow dung manure and soil to get the soil layer of 5 cm. Seed rate on each seedbed was 0.5 g and sown two days intervals. Seeds were covered by rice ash to prevent moisture losses and birds. Irrigation was done whenever necessary.

Transplanting procedure

In the field experiment, seedlings were transplanted with the age of 8, 10, 12 and 14 days for each variety (T₄, T₃, T₂ and T₁). Weed control was done on each 15 days interval of hand weeding and the weeds buried in soil as biomass organic matter. Adequate protection measures were given against pest and diseases.

Data Collection

Five random plants of each variety were taken from each plot and the collected data were-

Root length (cm)

Plant height (cm)

Number of tillers hill⁻¹

Number of effective tillers hill⁻¹

Filled grain percent

Number of spikelets panicle⁻¹

One thousand grains weight (g)

Grain yield (kg/ha)

Data Analysis

The data were subjected to analysis of variance designed in two factors factorial in CRD (Completely Randomized Design) by using the IRRISTATAS system software. Factor A assigned in rice varieties and Factor B assigned in treatments. Treatment means were separated with Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at 5 % level of significant.

Grain yield (t / ha) = No. of panicle m² × No. of grain per panicle × Percent of ripen grains × (Wt. of 1000 grains (g) ÷ 1000) × 1000

RESULTS

Table 1. Comparisons of diagnostic characters of five selected rice varieties

Variety name	Sinthukha	Shwewharhtun	Yarkyaw	Manawthukha	Byauehtun
Life span DAS	140	145	145	135	145
Plant height (cm)	107	130	120	105	120
No. of effective tillers	10_12	10_12	15	10_12	10_12
Leaf blade (cm)	27.3 - 55.5	50.2 - 86.1	50.2 - 86.1	29.3 - 73.8	47.0 - 70.0
Leaf sheath (cm)	20 - 25	22 - 33.5	25 - 32.5	15 - 20	25.0 - 34.0
Ligule shape	acute	acuminate	two-cleft	acute	acuminate
50 % flowering DAS	110	115	115	105	115
Panicle length cm	24.9	26.4	25.5	22.5	25.5
Stamen	6	6	6	6	6
Filament (mm)	6	6.2-6.5	6	6	6
Anther(mm)	1.6-2.0	2.0-2.1	2	1.8-2.0	1.8-2.0
Ovary(mm)	1	1	1	1	1
Style (mm)	2	2	2	2	2
Stigma	plumose	plumose	plumose	plumose	plumose

The important soil properties were measured before and after getting organic matter were tested. After cultivation of green manure, N, P and K contents of the soil were higher than before cultivation of green manure. Before cultivation of green manure, total N % 0.12, available P 2.48 and exchangeable cation K was 0.19 meq / 100 gm. After cultivation of green manure, total N % 0.20, P 35.03 and K value was increased compared to before cultivation of green manure but may not reach the requirement amount of crop uptake.

According to table (2), there was no significant effect of seedling age on root length in their growth of transplant and reproductive stage. Although the highest root length was observed in Byauehtun variety at their vegetative stage. In Shwewharhtun variety had the highest root length in their reproductive stage. In present study, there was no interaction between the variety and seedlings age.

Table 2. Mean effect of seedling age on root length for five rice varieties

	Root length (cm)		
	Transplant stage	Vegetative stage	Reproductive stage
Varieties			
V ₁	2.27	24.05	30.45
V ₂	2.46	29.65	69
V ₃	3.24	26.35	31.15
V ₄	4.78	23	60.5
V ₅	2.81	30.5	34.55
F-test	**	**	ns
LSD (5%)	2.16	3.26	45.21
CV (%)	110.2	19.4	193.5
Seedling ages			
T ₁	4.82	25.28	58
T ₂	3.19	28.96	31.56
T ₃	2.45	26.24	29.44
T ₄	1.92	26.32	29.52
F-test	*	ns	ns
LSD (5%)	1.93	2.92	40.44
CV (%)	110.2	19.4	193.5

Table 3. Mean effect of seedling age on plant height for five rice varieties.

	Plant Height (cm)		
	Transplant stage	Vegetative stage	Reproductive stage
Varieties			
V ₁	22.14	66.7	95.6
V ₂	20.19	68.96	106.75
V ₃	20.85	63.96	101.75
V ₄	18.88	62.5	86.8
V ₅	20.86	59.5	94.3
F-test	**	**	**
LSD (5%)	1.88	3.75	3.53
CV (%)	14.5	9.3	5.8
Seedling ages			
T ₁	25.88	64.16	95.32
T ₂	22.27	64.85	97.76
T ₃	15.91	65.54	97.84
T ₄	18.27	62.75	97.04
F-test	**	ns	ns
LSD (5%)	1.68	3.35	3.16
CV (%)	14.5	9.3	5.8

In present study, plant heights were highly significant in all stages for all five varieties. Generally, it can be noted that plant height increased as the seedling age increase. Among five rice varieties, the maximum means plant height was observed in Shwewharhtun variety. The minimum means plant height was in Manawthukha variety. The plant heights were not influenced by different seedlings age because of their varietal characteristics (Table 3).

Table 4. Mean effect of seedlings age on tillering for five rice varieties

Factors	No. of Tiller	
	Vegetative stage	Reproductive stage
Varieties		
V ₁	23.1	34.15
V ₂	23.5	30.65
V ₃	20.65	28.55
V ₄	23.35	28.9
V ₅	22.4	29.2
LSD (5%)	2.26	3.14
CV (%)	15.9	16.5
Seedling ages		
T ₁	21.52	28.96
T ₂	22.28	30.16
T ₃	24.16	31.16
T ₄	22.44	30.88
F-test	ns	ns
LSD (5%)	2.02	2.81
CV (%)	15.9	16.5

In table 4, tiller numbers were no significant in their reproductive stage. Maximum tillers were observed at Sinthukha variety and the second highest was observed in Yarkyaw variety. Among the five varieties, Manawthukha variety had the lowest tillers number. There was no significant in different seedling ages. The means tiller numbers were ranged from 28.96 to 30.88 respectively.

Table 5. Mean effect of seedlings age on effective tillering, Spikelet per panicle and filled grain for five rice varieties

Factors	Effective Tiller Hill ⁻¹	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹	Filled Grain panicle ⁻¹
	Reproductive stage		Filled grain (%)
Varieties			
V ₁	27.75	19.77	86.45
V ₂	21.45	20.06	85.4
V ₃	20.15	18.77	62.2
V ₄	23.1	18.48	87.68
V ₅	22	19.72	86.07
F-test	**	ns	**
LSD (5%)	2.52	1.55	16.47
CV (%)	17.5	12.7	32.1
Seedling ages			
T ₁	21.8	18.75	70.52
T ₂	22.88	19.85	78.15
T ₃	23.04	19.66	84.96
T ₄	23.84	19.17	92.61
F-test	ns	ns	*
LSD (5%)	2.26	1.39	14.73
CV (%)	17.5	12.7	32.1

There was no significant effect of different seedling age on effective tiller numbers. The minimum effective tillers were observed in 8 days old seedling and the second was observed in 10 days old seedling. According to the result data, Sinthukha variety had the highest effective tillers and Yarkyaw had the lowest.

Filled grain percent was highly significant between the five rice varieties. Among the varieties, Manawthukha was the highest (87.6%) and the lowest in Yarkyaw was (62.2%). The second highest was Sinthukha (86.45%). Comparison between the seedling ages, 8 days old seedling had the maximum filled grain percent and 10 days old seedling had the second filled grain percent. The result of present study indicated that filled grain percent of younger seedlings age were comparatively higher than older seedling.

The effect of seedling age on number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ was not significantly different. The highest spikelet number was observed in Shwewharhtun and the second highest was Sinthukha variety. Mean spikelets number of 12 days old seedling was higher than 8, 10 and 14 days old seedling. In this experiment, Spikelets per panicle was related with filled grain percent and grain yield.

Table 6. Mean effect of seedlings age on one thousand grain weight and grain yield for five rice varieties

Factors	1000 Grains weight (g)	Grain Yield (kg ha ¹)
Varieties		
V ₁	21	206211
V ₂	25.25	192405
V ₃	22.5	97129.2
V ₄	20	173875
V ₅	21.75	165660
F-test	*	*
LSD (5%)	3.28	58629
CV (%)	0	55.8
Seedling ages		
T ₁	21.6	119433
T ₂	22.8	155714
T ₃	21.2	184057
T ₄	22.8	209022
F-test	ns	ns
LSD (5%)	2.93	52439.8
CV (%)	0	55.8

Mean effect of seedlings age on 1000 grains weight are shown in Table 6. One thousand grains weight was significantly different. Shwewharhtun variety had the highest thousand grains weight. One thousand grains weight ranged from 20 to 25.25 g. In this study, 10 old seedlings was observed maximum 1000 grain weight (25.25 g). The minimum grains weight was observed in 10 days old seedling. In present study, there was significant effect of variety on grain yield.

Among the five varieties, Sinthukha was observed the highest grain yield and Yarkyaw was the lowest. Table 6, showed the mean yield of 10 days old seedling was higher than the other three. No interaction was observed between variety and seedling age factor. This means that the yield changes in different seedlings age were not influenced by variety. It was observed that maximum yield in each variety was result from 8 days old seedling. Grain yield were generally decreased as the seedlings age were increased. The result of present study revealed that young seedling age could increase grain yield.

Discussion and Conclusion

According to the results, the outstanding morphological characters of *Oryza sativa* L. were: perennial, the culm is made up of a series of nodes and internodes in alternate order, the blade of the leaf is attached to the node by the leaf sheath, the panicle is a group of spikelets, the stigma is a plumose structure. These findings were in agreement with Chang and Bardenas (1965) and Yoshida (1981). According to the soil analysis data, NPK in the study area were increased after using green manure. It was agreed with Shamauddin (1994).

According to the soil analysis data, NPK in the study area were increased after using green manure. It was agreed with Shamauddin (1994). He stated that including root nodules with leguminous plants as green manure crop can be increased the growth of paddy and soil fertility.

In present study, the maximum mean root length was 50 cm and plant root growth is greatly affected by soil environment. The incorporation of organic manure into soil can bring beneficial effects on crop root growth by improving physical and chemical environments of rhizosphere soil (Sudiraset *et al.*, 2001). SRI method may cause the increase in total canopy photosynthesis, which resulted in improved growth substantially (Thakur 2001).

Among five rice varieties, the maximum mean plant height was observed in Shwewharhtun variety. Shwewharhtun is a mutant variety and the plant height was about 120 cm. The plant heights were not influenced by different seedling ages because of their varietal characteristics. Among the seedling ages, 10 days old seedling showed the highest plant height and the lowest plant height was observed in 14 days old seedling. Maximum tillers were observed at Sinthukha variety and the second highest was observed in Yarkyaw variety. Tiller numbers of young seedling ages were higher than old seedling ages because of 8 and 10 days old seedling had maximum tiller number.

By weeding every 10-12 days interval, active soil aeration enhances plant performance in many ways (Bancy and Nyamai 2009). The result of present study revealed that 1000 grains weight is the varietal characteristic with least variation. The highest filled grain percent and grain yields were observed in 8 and 10 days old seedling. Evan (2001) suggested that paddy managed under SRI has shown good increase in yield.

Double yields are not difficult to achieve and some farmers have achieved up to 4 times their normal yield. By comparing the growth and yield of young seedling ages with those of old seedlings under system of rice cultivation (SRI), 8 and 10 days old seedling were significantly higher than those of 12 and 14 days old seedling. Chris Evans (2001) stated that the seedling grown in the nursery beds are transplanted after just 8-10 days or at the 2-leaf stage.

Moreover, organic manure is found very beneficial for SRI method, but in the case of less fertile soil, farmers should use a balance dose of fertilizer for more yields. Among the five rice varieties, Sinthukha variety performed the better growth and yield when young seedling (≤ 10 days) was used with the effect of green manure. There was no interaction between variety and seedling age at their growth and yields at all stages.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the concept of SRI technology can be applied as an alternative rice cultivation system for high yield production for local farmers. Further studies are needed to identify the potential of SRI technology under different ecosystems of rice cultivation by using green manure.

References

- Bor N. L. (1960). *The Grasses of Burma, Ceylon, India and Parkistan*. Oxford, Ledon, Newyork.
- Evant C. (2013). *Appropriate technology in Asia*. Kathmandu Nepal.
- Hooker, J. D. (1897). *The Flora of British India*, Vol. VII. L. Reeve and Co. Ltd. England.
- Kumar P., A. Mishra and A. Noble. (2013). *Assessing the potential of SRI management principles and the FFS approach in Northeast Thailand for sustainable rice intensification in the contex of climate change*. International Journal of Agriculture.
- Muta C. A and Kindt R, Jamnadass R, S Anthony. (2009). *Agroforestree based cropping systems in South Asia*. The International Rice Research Institute in collaboration with the Commission on the Application of Science to Agriculture, forestry and Aquaculture.
- MAI. (2004). *Rice Varieties in Myanmar*. Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation, Union of Myanmar.
- RA M. and D. P. Garrity. (1994). *Green Manures in rice- wheat cropping systems in Asia*. International Rice Research Institute (IRRI).
- Shamauddin. (1994). *Management of Biological Nitrogen Fixation for the Development of More Productive and Sustainable Agricultural Systems*. Mexico: Agriculture at the 15th Congress of Soil Science, Acapulco.
- Thakur P. (2001). *Effective for rice plant morphology and physiology of water and associated mg practices of SRI and their implication for crop performance*. PAWE.
- Yoshida, S. (1981). *Growth and Development of the Rice Plant*. In Fundamentals of rice crop science. The International Rice Research Institute (IRRI).